

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Social Environments + Social Studies: An article review on the factors contributing the Learning of Geography as a Social Studies Discipline

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Abstract

This article review contains critical and constructive analysis on different literatures that determined the contribution of Social Environments on students' learning of Geography as a Social Studies Discipline in rely with the Functionalist Theory of Emile Durkheim and Social Learning Theory of Albert Bandura. With a qualitative approach as article review design, the proponent utilized the documentary analysis (involves repeated review, examination, and interpretation of the data in order to gain meaning and empirical knowledge) of the construct being studied on the deciphered research journal articles from different peer-reviewed journals from the Google Scholar. The review disclosed that there is a significant relationship between Social Environments (family, school, peers and community) and students' academic performance in Geography as part of the Social Studies curriculum was drawn. In accordance to, the Functionalist Theory and Social Learning Theory are reliable assumptions in regards to the contribution of Social Environments on students' learning of Geographical knowledge and skills.

Keywords: Social Environments, Geography learning, Social Studies Discipline, academic performance, Documentary analysis

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1.Introduction

Department of Education (DepEd) emphasized that the education sector should consider their stakeholders in preparation of their institutional planning for better academe; to contribute time effort and resources (DepEd Order No. 43, s. 2017). Likewise, "Social Environments" present in our society are the stakeholders of the educational landscape in the Philippines that can be considered. Moreover, in the aspect of teaching-learning process, these entities should be appraised on how they can contribute to the academic success or failure of the students.

In consonance with the idea above, Social Studies (Araling Panlipunan) is one of the curricular disciplines in K-12 Basic Education Curriculum in the country that tends to develop 21st Century "functionally literate Filipino" with the help of society. However, as this subject is very broad, multidisciplinary and integrative, this paper wanted to focus only on one of its sub-fields which is Geography. This incorporated discipline in Social Studies curriculum provide students extensive knowledge and critical

understanding on the dynamics of human-environment relations that is why Dizon (2021) pondered that there should be a separate subject intended for this area of discipline. Gil and Gestura (2021) added that Geography education has an anticipated space in the Social Studies curriculum that the skills and knowledge to be developed on students' academic performance may be used to interpret and analyze future.

Regardless of how, various contributions from Social Environments in learning Geography as an embedded discipline for Social Studies shall continuously be assessed by curricularists and educational researchers for the improvement of its educational sphere.

This article review wanted to scan several research journals that depict the contributions of Social Environments on learning Geography as a Social Studies discipline. The theoretical basis of this article was derived from the major learning theories and these were examined in terms of their appropriateness for the essence of this review. As to go deeper, the proponent wanted to see the reliability of these theories on the concern